

New organisational and social provision in Sweden

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1. Introduction

Since 2011 there is on-going work at the Swedish Work Environment Authority (SWEA) to come up with a new provision regulating the area of organisational and social conditions in the work environment. During the last 15 years SWEA has made two efforts to come up with new provisions in this area but on both occasions the work has been cancelled for various reasons.

The aim of the work is to create prerequisites for a good work environment considering organisational, psychological and social factors by delivering a new general provision of the area. In addition to the provision guidance will be delivered with the aim to support and explain to the reader how to fulfill the provision.

At the moment there are mainly two provisions and a general advice that cover the area; Victimization at Work, Patient Care in Private Homes and General Advice on Psychological and Social Aspects of the Work Environment. These provisions and general advice have not been revised the last 20-30 years so there is a need to make a thorough revision. Also, regulations considering prevention of unhealthy work related stress will be included in the new provision.

The European Stress Agreement which has been signed by the parties on the Swedish labour market is used as one of the inspirational documents when producing the provision. Also, the European Framework Agreement on Harassment and Violence at Work is of interest for the work. Another document of interest is the former draft provision that was stopped 2004.

2. Methods

The work is carried out according to SWEA's process how to develop a provision. The process is divided into five main parts – planning the work, write text of provision, internal remittance, external remittance and approval of provision.

Also, the new provision must be easily understood by the expected reader, hence the text of the provision is read and commented by an external linguistic reviewer. In addition, the provision is used in field tests with expected users followed-up by focus group discussions to improve the understandability further.

Another part of the process is to investigate the consequences of the provision in terms of costs and revenue for the employer.

3. Results

At the moment the provision covers the following main areas:

- setting of goals in relation to social and organisational factors,
- unhealthy workload,
- working hours,
- knowledge and
- discourage of insults and harassments.

Due to ongoing work this list of main areas might be changed during the period to NES 2014 conference.

The plan is that the provision will enter into force in Autumn 2015 but before that it has been sent out on internal remittance to inspection districts in Spring 2014 and will be sent out on external remittance to employer organisations, trade unions and other Swedish authorities in Autumn 2014. Of course it is possible for any organization or person in Sweden to give their opinion on the provision by downloading the external remittance from SWEA's internet site.

At NES 2014 we will present the results of the work so far and some reflections/complications.